

Solar Photovoltaic Materials: A Review and Future Directions

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Abstract

Purpose – The purpose of this paper is to review research on Solar Photovoltaic Material development and usage in world and to find out the probable improvements at user level which can be experimented and applied later on .The research aims to identify gaps in the current body of knowledge, which justifies future research directions.

Design/Methodology/approach – Using literature review (LR) method, the present study reviews articles from secondary sources on relevant themes.

Findings – Detailed content analysis reveals that the research work is descriptive and paves way for experimental research .It highlights that the various stakeholders expect cost reduction , increased conversion efficiencies , improved manufacturing and throughput , improved Quality and Reliability , Achieving Grid Parity , using Environmentally Green Panels .Also, the risks associated with Acid Rain, Lightning, Earthquakes should also be taken care apart from the electrical risks.

Practical implications –Research paper focuses on what factors that have an effect on efficiency of solar panels and suggests some small improvements which can be implemented after feasibility check at user level like usage of wipers on solar panels to wipe out dust at regular frequencies which can increase daily output. The paper also discusses how Quality Function Deployment can be used as a tool for quality improvement for Solar Photovoltaic Materials.

Originality/value –The research paper proposes an Ishikawa diagram for efficiency of solar panels which lists many factors that have an effect on efficiency of solar panels based on literature review and feedback from stakeholders .Further it exemplifies the usage of FMEA for product and process which can give inputs for developing better designed panels.

Keywords: Solar Photovoltaic panels, Failure Mode Effect Analysis, Grid Parity, Cost Reduction, Quality Function Deployment

1. Introduction

The scarcity of fossil fuels and the rapid rate of their consumption have forced the world to explore renewable sources of energy .At current consumption rates it is estimated that world coal reserves could last for about 120 years, oil for approximately 45 years and natural gas for around 60 years .Renewable Sources of Energy are defined as “Energy flows which are replenished at the same rate as they are used.” (Sorensen, 2000)

Figure 1.1 Percentage Contributions to World Primary Energy Consumption in 2009 (Boyle, 2013) .(Other sources include new biomass , solar and geothermal energy and energy from wind , wave , tide and wastes)

Figure1.2 Percentage Contribution of Individual Renewable Energy Sources contribution to world primary energy supplies in 2008 (Boyle, 2013)

According to (Boyle, 2013) Sun is the primary source of renewable energy. Approximately 30% of the 5.4 million EJ per year arriving at earth is reflected back into space. The remaining 70 % is available for

use on earth and amounts to approximately 3.8 million EJ, more than 8200 times the rate of consumption of Fossil and Nuclear fuels ,Hydro Power, Bio Fuels in 2009, some 502 EJ where $1 \text{ EJ} = 10^{18} \text{ J}$.Solar Radiation is either direct or diffused and can be used for various direct and indirect uses. Solar Photovoltaic Cells use Solar Energy directly to generate electricity.

Figure 1.3 various methods for Solar Energy Utilization (Sukhatme, 1996)

Photovoltaic is derived from words photos (Greek word for light) and volt (name of the unit for potential difference).Photovoltaic's means the generation of electricity from light. Conventional PV consists of a P-Type (Silicon doped with Group 3 element of periodic table) and N-type Semiconductor (Silicon doped with group 5 element of periodic table) .P-type semiconductors have holes in majority and N-type semiconductors have electrons in majority .

Figure 1.4 PV Cell (DH Lighting)

When a p-n junction is formed the holes in the p-type semiconductor gets attracted to the electrons in the n-type. This creates a layer around the junction in the p-type which is more negative than usual and a layer which is more positive than usual . This sets up a reverse electric field near the junction and the region near the junction becomes a depletion zone with scarcity of charge carriers. The electrons stimulated by the photons to move to conduction band tend to roll downwards in the n-region and the photons tend to move upwards towards in the p-region under the influence of electric field. The electron moves out through one of the metallic contacts and the hole through the opposite contact . (K.L Gomber, 2001) (Boyle, 2013)

The PV installation capacity has increased in manifolds over the past few years as shown below .

Figure 1.5 Evolution of Global PV Capacity in various regions of the world (Boyle, 2013)

2. Objectives

The major objectives of the research paper are –

- To find out the expectations of various stakeholders of Solar PV Industries .
- To review research on Solar Photovoltaic (SPV) Material Development and Applications with respect to efficiency , cost and environmental Impact .
- To look into the possibilities of some user level improvements in solar panels taking inputs from literature review and SPV user feedback.
- To find out the gaps in the current body of knowledge which will justify future research directions

3. Research Methodology

Table 1 Research Design ,Research and Data Type

Term	Type Used and Description
Research Design	Exploratory as it involves secondary data Descriptive because it involves verbal feedback of users of solar panels
Research Type	Exploratory Descriptive (all information related to solar panels is listed)
Sampling Type	Simple Random Sampling – Of the many installers in Jaipur few were contacted on phone to collect data regarding dust problem .First Jaipur was selected as the area using Multi Stage sampling
Data Source	Books and Papers ,verbal feedback of installers on panels
Data Type	Secondary Data (Data from books , journal papers) Primary Data (Observations of installers)
Variables Involved	Shown in Cause and Effect Diagram of efficiency Cost related parameters Environmental impact related parameters

4. Expectations of Stakeholders in Solar PV Industry

Figure 4.1 Stakeholders for Solar PV Industry

Based on our conversation with various stakeholders the following expectations were listed –

1. Cost Reduction
2. Increasing Conversion Efficiencies
3. Improving Manufacturing and Throughput
4. Improving Quality and Reliability
5. Achieving Grid Parity
6. Using Environmentally Green Panels (Conversation with Stakeholders (Mitesh Nandu (Sales representative) , Gurpreet Singh (Employee-Ajit Solar Power Limited,Jaipur), Rajesh Yadav (Employee-Solar Max Industry ,Jaipur),Inder Singh (Employee-Rays Experts Limited))

5.Types of Solar Photovoltaic Materials ,Efficiency of Materials and Cost Impact

The various types of Solar Photovoltaic Materials are shown below :

Figure 5.1 Types of Solar Photovoltaic Materials (Boyle, 2013)

Figure 5.2 Cell and Module Efficiencies for various types (Lumby, Feb 2012)

The monocrystalline, polycrystalline and thin films PV Modules are all commercialized except Gallium Arsenide which is only used in spacecraft applications. The other PV technologies (Organic Solar Cells and Multi-junction Technologies) were at the research and development stage and are yet to be commercialized hence minimum and maximum module efficiency are not known . (Lumby, Feb 2012)

Figure 5.3 Global Installed Capacity in 2010

Figure 5.4 Thickness of Crystalline and thin Film PV Cells

Figure 5.5 Cost per watt installed for various PV module types

Figure 5.6 Temperature coefficient /°C for Cryst.& TF PV

Note : Source for Figure 5.4 - 5.6 (Lumby, Feb 2012)

From the above figures we can conclude that –

1. Crystalline Silicon modules have 63% greater efficiency than the most efficient thin film technology
2. Crystalline Silicon modules are 200-300 times thicker than the thin film PV modules which have a thickness less than 1 μm and have a much higher cost probably because high material usage .
3. Crystalline silicon modules have a much higher temperature coefficient per degree centigrade. **Temperature coefficient shows how power output of the solar panel module depends on cell temperature .**
4. 78 % of the modules installed globally are made from crystalline silicon .

Figure 5.8 Overview of solar PV Power Plant (Lumby, Feb 2012)

The risks associated with Acid Rain, Lightning, Earthquakes should also be taken care apart from the electrical risks.Based on the Literature review we have done till date the Efficiency of solar panels depends on large number of factors as listed under **Man , Machine , Material , Method and Environment** category . **The cause and effect diagram also known as Ishikawa was used to list all the probable factors which can have an effect on efficiency.** Man, Machine, Material, Method and

Figure 5.9 Ishikawa Diagram for Efficiency of Solar Panels (Based on Literature Review till date)

- a) Single AXIS Tracking mechanisms increase the efficiency by 25 % . (Boyle, 2013)
- b) Safe transport and proper machine handling are to be ensured for better efficiency.
- c) In the material category Crystalline cells have a better efficiency than Amorphous Cells . (Lumby, Feb 2012)
- d) The Multi-junction type cells have maximum lab efficiencies of around 40 % and the practical efficiencies of 28 % . **Efficiency can be increased by processing the material in such a way that the grains are relatively large in size and oriented in a top to bottom direction to allow light to penetrate deeply into each grain, these and other improvements have enabled commercially available polycrystalline PV modules to reach efficiencies of over 15 percent .** (Boyle, 2013)
- e) The highly rough surface absorbs light readily as the absorption coefficient is high. Anti-Reflective coating is also applied on the surface to reduce reflection from surface.
- f) Concentrating Collectors have better efficiency as compared to flat plate collectors as Solar radiation is of 2 types -Direct and Diffused Radiation. (Sukhatme, 1996)
- g) As the SPV's rarely have any moving part except the tracking mechanisms and the manual impact is limited to material handling and testing. Failsafe methods should be used so that any

test is not skipped .The robustness of the installation plays an important role so that sudden changes in weather conditions can be taken care of .

- h) In the methods category the collection of accurate data related to Solar Energy is highly important as it helps us to prepare for uncertainties. Machine and Process capabilities of processes like diffusion and edge isolation , texturing and application of anti-reflective coatings is also important along with establishment of cleaning frequency /method of panels .
- i) **Software for Data Collection and Site Specific Selection of Materials can play an important role in being prepared for uncertainties.** Soft ware’s available in market for collection of Solar Energy Data (PVGIS -PV Geographical Information System) is the online tool developed by European union joint research centre at ISPRA, ITALY. Users can input the geographic location, type of module, its power rating , array orientation and the software can calculate the expected monthly and annual energy yield) . (Boyle, 2013)
- j) The critical elements in mitigating risk in Solar PV Power Plants are –1. Ensuring that there is high quality on-site measured irradiation data available for MW scale PV projects, ,selection of right satellite data source and the use of the same is very critical to reduce uncertainties (and so risks in energy yield assessment).**Track record of main equipment suppliers and suitability of the technology for the conditions of the site are a key aspect to ensure the profitability of the PV plant .** (Francesco, 2013)
- k) **Testing methods for Thermal cycling, Humidity and freezing, Mechanical stress and twist, Hail resistance and Performance under some fixed test conditions Standard Testing Conditions (STC) are established complying to various International and National Standards .** (Lumby, Feb 2012) .**Some national and international testing standards are listed below :**

Table 2 Some national and international testing standards related to Solar Panels (Lumby, Feb 2012)

Test Standard	Description	Comment
IEC 61215	Crystalline silicon terrestrial photovoltaic (PV) modules – Design qualification and type approval.	The standard certification uses a 2,400 Pa pressure. Modules in heavy snow locations may be tested under more stringent 5,400 Pa conditions.

IEC 61646	Thin-film terrestrial photovoltaic (PV) modules – Design qualification and type approval.	Very similar to the IEC 61215 certification, but an additional test specifically considers the additional degradation of thin film modules.
EN/IEC 61730	PV module safety qualification.	Part 2 of the certification defines three different .Application Classes: 1). Safety Class 0 – Restricted access applications.2). Safety Class II – General applications.3). Safety Class III – Low voltage applications.
IEC 60364-4-41	Protection against electric shock.	Module safety assessed based on:1). Durability.2). High dielectric strength.3). Mechanical stability.4). Insulation thickness and distances.
IEC 61701	Resistance to salt mist and corrosion	Required for modules being installed near the coast or for maritime applications
Conformité Européenne (EC)	The certified product conforms to the EU health, safety and environmental requirements.	Mandatory in the European Economic Area .
UL 1703	Comply with the National Electric Code (NEC), OSHA and the National Fire Prevention Association. The modules perform to at least 90% of the manufacturer's nominal power.	Underwriters Laboratories Inc. (UL) is an independent U.S.-based product safety testing certification company which is a Nationally Recognised Testing Laboratory (NRTL) Certification by a NRTL is mandatory in the U.S

2. Sun is a dilute source of energy. Even in the hottest regions on earth , the solar flux available rarely exceeds 1 KW/m² .These are low values from the point of view of technical utilization and consequently large collecting areas are required in many applications and these result in excessive

costs .The availability varies with time , Variation occurs because of the day-night cycle and also seasonally because of the earth’s orbit around the sun .In addition variations occur at a specific location because of local weather conditions . Consequently, the need for storage for use when it is not available also adds significantly to the cost of any system .**Hence the real challenge in utilizing solar energy as an energy alternative is of an economic nature. Hence cheaper methods of collection and storage are required so that large initial investments required at present in most applications are reduced.** (Sukhatme, 1996).

The reduction of Cost of Solar Panels for GRID PARITY to be reached i.e (Cost of PV Power becomes comparable with that of conventional utility supplier).**For this the installation cost per kilowatt hr of POWER** systems need to decrease which can decrease with mass production of parts .

During the last 30 years following approaches for cost and efficiency optimization are used –

- 1.Use of polycrystalline silicon ,
2. Growing silicon in ribbon form ,
- 3.Use of other crystalline PV materials such as Gallium Arsenide (Boyle, 2013)

Figure 5.11 : Cost per KW hour of Solar Power from SPV’s (Boyle, 2013)

3. Search for Fire Proof & Electrically Safe Materials as the concerns highlighted during the Environmental Impact Assessment are listed below -

Figure 5.12 : Environmental Impact Assessment of Solar Panels (Boyle, 2013)

- a) Solar cells having **CdTe , CIS** use very small quantities of **Indium , Cadmium , Tellurium** and there is a **slight risk of fire** in an array which might cause small amount of **toxic materials** containing these elements to be released into environment .
- b) Some **toxic materials are used during production**. eg :Cadmium is a Toxic Material .
- c) **Aesthetics improvement of Solar Cells as visual impact is a concern. Some people do not find it as a pleasant site if they see Solar Panels on roof-top or in nearby areas.** (Boyle, 2013)

Figure 5.13: Designs inspired by natural world to improve aesthetics. (Sowden)

6. User level Improvements in Solar Panels

Example :To find out whether dust impacts efficiency of panels or not .

Ways of testing effect of dust on solar panels are -

Table 6.1 Feedback from installers on whether dust impacts efficiency or not

Installer Name	Representative Name	Dust impacts efficiency (Yes/No)
Saurabh Misra	Rays Power	Yes

Ajit Solar	Gurpreet Singh	Yes
Rays Experts Limited	Inder Singh	Yes
Arsh Solar and Lights	Name not disclosed	Yes
Galaxy Solar Energy Pvt Ltd	Name not disclosed	Yes

Hypothesis	Statement
Ho	It is believed that all the people feel that dust does not impact efficiency.
Ha	It is believed that all the people feel that dust does impact efficiency.

Number of people = 5 , possible outcomes =2 opinions (dust impacts efficiency , dust doesnot impact efficiency) ,It is a dichotomous experiment hence binomial theorem is applicable .

Total possible outcomes with respect to all 5 people = $2*2*2*2*2 = 32$

Number of cases where all people feel that dust impacts efficiency = 1

$P = \text{Success} = \text{dust doesnot impact efficiency} = 31/32 = 0.96875$

$q = \text{Failure} = \text{dust impacts efficiency} = 1/32 = 0.03125$ (Note :The 1/32 is based on primary data)

So , probability of getting 0,1,2,3,4,5 successes based on Bernoulli's theorem is calculated below .

Table 3 Table for expected and observed frequency

Number of Successes	Expected Probability	Observed Probability	(o-e)	(o-e) ²	(o-e) ² /e
0	2.98023E-08	0.853215188	0.853215	0.727976	24426824.74
1	4.61936E-06	0.137615353	0.137611	0.018937	4099.423751
2	0.0002864	0.00887841	0.008592	7.38E-05	0.257760286
3	0.00887841	0.0002864	-0.00859	7.38E-05	0.008314848
4	0.137615353	4.61936E-06	-0.13761	0.018937	0.137606114
5	0.853215188	2.98023E-08	-0.85322	0.727976	0.853215128
					24430925.42

The Chi Square Calculated value = 24430925.42 and Chi Square Tabulated at 0.05 and 4 degree of freedom is 9.488 and hence null hypothesis is rejected. Hence dust impacts efficiency.

Figure 6.1 Factors affecting dust accumulation on solar panels

Note :The effect of orientation and tilt is not much critical . (Boyle, 2013)

FMEA is used (Failure Mode Effect Analysis – Product and Process) for better prevention and detection measures of design and process problems. Design FMEA is prepared during product preparation and will consist of all design related characteristics of Solar Panels and their possible failure modes and causes and prevention and detection actions for same .When Solar Panels are sold to the consumer then he/she will be given a set of instructions usually enclosed in manuals as do’s and dont’s in case of failure which will list some basic measures in case the product stops working or is not fulfilling the expectation of the customers .for eg : Low Efficiency which may be due to dust accumulation .

Table 6.2 Failure Mode Effect Analysis for Solar Panel (2011)

S. No	Product (Component)	Function	Failure Mode	Failure Effect	Critical Characteristics	Failure Cause	Preventive Measures	Detection Measures	Severity (S)	Occurrence (O)	Detection (D)	RPN (Risk Priority Number)	Action
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					(C)							mber)	
1	Solar Panel	Generation of electricity from Sun Rays	Dirt accumulation on surface	Reduced Efficiency	C	Soil erosion with winds, can happen anytime there are winds	Daily Manual cleaning before start	Visual Inspection	8	2	8	128	
							Covering of panels based on weather forecasting	Sensors placed to detect dirt and automatic water spray introduced after dirt accumulation	8	1	7	56	Limit to be decided for dirt accumulation after which sensor will start
							Using Dirt Resistant Material		8	1	7	56	
							Finding optimum level of surface roughness of surface.		8	1	7	56	

							Introduction of remote operated automatic cleaner (dust removing cloth)with rolling or sliding mechanism (feasibility to be checked)		8	1	7	56	
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Hence , we can use better materials ,upgrade /improve existing materials to achieve better functional performance . The functions of solar panels are 1.Power Generation 2.Achieving the specified efficiency 3.Achieving other product specifications as their failures lead to functional failures .

7. Conclusions

The current problem is that because of scarcity of non- renewable sources of energy the usage of renewable sources of energy is required and solar energy which is available in abundance is a very good prospect .Different types of solar cell materials are available , the non-commercial solar cells are still not widely used and hence the focus will be on-

1.Fabricating and Characterizing Alternative Materials with Increased Efficiency, Reduced Cost , low environmental impact i.e Environmentally Green and Safe Panels

The properties of various materials shall be investigated and then changes can be induced in the structure to obtain better properties .The structure is a function of processing (Callister)so into manufacturing methods will be looked into to optimize performance . The Futuristic and Novel Technologies can be explored (Abdi) in Solar Photovoltaic’s which are not commercialized yet. The analysis of existing efficiencies and formulation of hypothesis to validate their correctness can be done .

2.The emerging PV technologies are listed below :

Figure 7.1: Emerging PV Technologies (Boyle, 2013)

Dye Sensitized Solar Cells Work like Photoelectrochemical Cells where 2 glass plates have SnO₂ and titanium oxide is applied along with a sensitizer and iodine based electrolyte is in between the 2 cells. Nanotechnology aims to manipulate molecules and atoms at extremely small scales , measured in billionth of a meter , or nanometres .Nano particles consisting of extremely small collections of atoms ranging from just a few up to around 10000 of semiconducting material are called quantum dots . The band gaps of quantum dots can be tuned to different parts of the solar spectrum by changing their size .With QD's of a variety of sizes, more of the energy in the spectrum can be absorbed. PV cells using quantum dots are theoretically capable of very high efficiencies but are still at the R & D stage, current efficiencies in laboratories are around 5 % . (Boyle, 2013)

3.Dust accumulation is a hindrance in obtaining maximum efficiency and the measures like automatic cleaner , optimization of surface roughness ,dust repellent surfaces are measures which can result in improvement .

4.The expectations of customers if fulfilled can increase their satisfaction levels and will result in innovations by the customer , for the customer and of the customer .

5.The various type of risks (occurrence(quantity of occurrence) * impact (severity of effect)) which can be addressed using Failure Mode Effect Analysis are shown below .

Figure 7.2 Risks which can be addressed in FMEA related to Solar Power Plants (Lumby, Feb 2012)

8. Future Prospects of Research–

1. Further review of literature on material efficiency and properties of non-commercialized materials can be done and through selection of alternate materials, fabrication, characterization, structure and performance optimization, mechanical and other property analysis can be done.

2. The future lies in fabricating and characterizing alternative Materials with

a) Increased Efficiency

b) Reduced Cost

c) Low Environmental Impact i.e Environmentally Green and Safe

3. Quality Function Deployment can be used as a tool to optimize the combination of factors causing improvement in efficiency, reduction in cost etc. The way to proceed for Quality Function Deployment is shown below. First take Customer Requirements and then list Technical Requirements and then using data analysis after collecting relevant data correlational and reliability studies can be done and

conclusions can be drawn to decide whether strong, moderate or weak relationship exists. Relations between technical requirements with each other can also be found out based on data. After that it can be decided which technical requirement should be maximized and which should be reduced to accomplish customer requirements in the best way possible.

Figure 8.1 Quality Function Deployment Basics (Chaturvedi Joohi, 2015)

Figure 8.2 Factors Influencing Purchasing of a Solar Panel (Choosing solar panels)

Legend		
	Strong Relationship	9
	Moderate Relationship	3
	Weak Relationship	1
	Strong Positive Correlation	
	Positive Correlation	
	Negative Correlation	
	Strong Negative Correlation	
	Objective Is To Minimize	
	Objective Is To Maximize	
	Objective Is To Hit Target	

Figure 8.2 Symbols used in quality function deployment

Customer (in rows) and Technical (in columns) Requirements	X	▼	▼	▲	▲	▲	▲	▲		X	X			▲
Type of material (Polycrystalline , Monocrystalline , Thin Film)														
Type of Glass (Tempered Glass , Flat Glass)														
Tilt Angle of panel														
Temperature Coefficient														
Light Induced Degradation Resistance														
Potential Induced Degradation Resistance														
Anti- Reflection Coating Material and Thickness														
Back Sheet thickness and material														
EVA Sheet thickness and material														
Type of junction (Single junction / Multi-junction P-N Junction)														
EVA Layer														
Quality Tests (Mechanical , Electrical tests)														
Solar Radiation Collection Mechanism														
Size of panels														
Type of Supplier (Tier 1 , Tier 2 , Tier 3)														
High Conversion Efficiency	○	○	○	○			○			○	○		○	○
High Durability	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
High Power												○	○	○
Low Cost	○				○	○							○	
High Strength											○			
High Safety	○				○	○					○			○

High Quality												⊖			⊖
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Figure 8.3 Initial steps in Quality Function Deployment

Note : Correlation symbols used in above diagram are based on perception and are not realistic.Thorough accuracy can be obtained from realistic data collection and analysis .

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